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Deliverable D1.4 – Final ERA Hub Framework model and KPIs

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Executive Summary

This deliverable, D1.4 – Final ERA Hub Framework Model and KPIs, presents an integrated, evidence-based framework for strengthening regional research and innovation (R&I) ecosystems across Europe, primarily focusing on advancing knowledge valorisation. Through iterative co-design with a Co-Design Task Force (CDTF) and piloting in three regions of varying maturity, the project refined a model that:

- Defines ERA Hubs as university-led ecosystems of quadruple helix actors (academia, industry, government, and civil society) oriented toward creating social and economic value from knowledge.
- Identifies seven lines of action (Research, Talent, Knowledge Transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance, and Innovation) across which regional R&I ecosystems can assess their maturity.
- Sets four maturity levels—Emerging, Developing, Mature, and Advanced—each with corresponding indicators and pathways for improvement.
- Provides four implementation tools to operationalise the model and guide regions at every stage of development: COOPERATE Playbook (Hereinafter PLAYBOOK); COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool (Hereinafter SELF-ASSESSMENT); COOPERATE Toolbox (Hereinafter TOOLBOX); COOPERATE Platform (Hereinafter Platform).

The framework addresses Europe’s innovation challenges: fostering effective knowledge valorisation, bridging regional imbalances, and supporting university-led orchestration of regional R&I ecosystems. Deliverable 1.4 details this final ERA Hub Framework model and outlines the next steps toward full implementation across European regions.

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
CDTF	Co-Design Task Force
D	Deliverable
DX.X	Deliverable Number
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ERL	Ecosystem Readiness Level
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MLE	Mutual Learning Exercise
R&I	Research and Innovation
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Glossary of Key Terms

ERA Hub: An ecosystem of quadruple helix actors, led by universities, aiming at improving knowledge valorisation within their region.

Knowledge Valorisation: The process of creating social and economic value from knowledge by linking different sectors and transforming research results into sustainable products, services, solutions, and knowledge-based policies.

Quadruple Helix: A collaboration model involving four types of actors: academia, industry, government, and civil society.

Ecosystem Readiness Level (ERL): A scale from 1-5 measuring the maturity of regional R&I ecosystems.

Maturity Levels: The stages (Emerging, Developing, Mature, Advanced) describing the progress of a regional R&I ecosystem across seven lines of action.

PLAYBOOK: Strategic guidance providing hallmarks of excellence and a roadmap for ecosystem development.

SELF-ASSESSMENT: Digital tool enabling ecosystem self-assessment across the seven lines of action.

TOOLBOX: Collection of 33 actionable interventions tailored to different ecosystem maturity levels.

PLATFORM: Digital infrastructure connecting ERA Hubs and providing access to implementation tools.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the final ERA Hub Framework Model developed through COOPERATE, a pilot project designed to strengthen university-led regional R&I ecosystems across Europe. The deliverable is a result of developing and testing an initial prototype of the ERA Hub Framework Model, which will require further refinement and expansion beyond the pilot phase.

The report begins with **Section 2: Background and Policy Context**, which establishes the foundation for the ERA Hub Framework Model by examining Europe's innovation challenges. This section outlines the critical need for knowledge valorisation—transforming research into societal and economic value—and explains how fragmented regional innovation ecosystems contribute to Europe's competitive gaps. It articulates why universities are uniquely positioned to coordinate regional innovation efforts and presents the value proposition of ERA Hubs in addressing persistent innovation barriers across Europe.

Building on this context, **Section 3: Methodology** reveals the evidence-based approach used to develop the framework. The section details how theoretical models were tested and refined through an iterative co-design process with the CDTF (Co-Design Task Force). It explains how pilot implementations across three diverse regions—representing different ecosystem maturity levels—provided critical insights that shaped the framework, ensuring it balances standardisation with the flexibility needed to accommodate regional differences.

Section 4: ERA Hub Framework Model: Current Prototype then presents the resulting framework, defining ERA Hubs as university-led ecosystems of quadruple helix actors (academia, industry, government, and civil society) focused on improving knowledge valorisation. The section outlines the governance model developed through the pilot phase and introduces seven interconnected lines of action—Research, Talent, Knowledge Transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance, and Innovation—that form the structural foundation of the framework. It also details how regional R&I ecosystems can be assessed across four maturity levels, from Emerging to Advanced, using radar chart visualisations.

The operationalisation of the Framework is detailed in **Section 5: ERA Hub Framework Model: Implementation Tools**, which introduces four complementary tools developed to operationalise the ERA Hub Framework Model. The PLAYBOOK provides hallmarks of excellence and a roadmap for the ERA Hub development process; the SELF-ASSESSMENT enables ecosystem maturity self-assessment; the TOOLBOX offers 33 actionable interventions tailored to different maturity levels across the seven lines of action; and the PLATFORM serves as both a resource repository for the aforementioned tools and digital infrastructure connecting regional R&I ecosystems across Europe. The section clarifies each tool's current prototype functionality and outlines what remains to be developed for full implementation.

Finally, **Section 6: Towards a Fully Developed ERA Hub Framework Model** looks beyond the pilot phase to envision a comprehensive Europe-wide implementation. It presents strategies for scaling the

framework through refined governance structures, improved stakeholder incentives, enhanced digital tools, and integration with complementary European R&I initiatives. The section concludes by examining how a fully developed ERA Hub Model could address Europe's innovation challenges by strengthening knowledge valorisation, reducing territorial inequalities, and driving collective innovation performance across regional R&I ecosystems.

This deliverable represents a significant milestone in developing a structured, evidence-based approach to strengthening knowledge valorisation across European regions, with universities serving as central orchestrators of increasingly mature regional R&I ecosystems.

2 Background and Policy Context

The European Union faces ongoing competitiveness challenges, reflected in an innovation gap relative to the United States and China. While Europe produces quality research and possesses considerable scientific capabilities, translating these strengths into commercial success varies across regions (Draghi, 2024). This situation provides context for the renewal of the European Research Area (ERA) - the EU's vision to create a more integrated market for R&I across Europe.

2.1 Why are ERA Hubs needed

Recent high-level policy documents—including the Draghi (2024) and Letta (2024) reports, the ERA Policy Agenda (2025-2027), and the Final Report of the Mutual Learning Exercise on Knowledge Valorisation (European Commission, 2022) identify four critical needs that ERA Hubs address.

2.1.1 Need to foster knowledge valorisation

Knowledge valorisation has evolved from a specific action item (ERA Action 7) in the 2022-2024 ERA Policy Agenda (European Commission, 2022) to a recognised structural policy in the 2025-2027 ERA Policy Agenda (European Commission, 2025). This elevation signifies its importance as a long-term, foundational element embedded in national and European policy frameworks.

The Draghi (2024, pp.28-29) report highlights this challenge noting that while “Europe has a strong position in fundamental research and patenting, unfortunately “much of the knowledge generated by European researchers remains commercially unexploited.” According to the European Patent Office, only about one-third of patented inventions registered by European universities or research institutions reach the commercial application stage.

The Final Report of the Mutual Learning Exercise on Knowledge Valorisation (European Commission, 2022, p.38) identified several critical paradigm shifts underway including the “shift from knowledge transfer to knowledge valorisation” and from “intellectual property to intellectual assets”. Knowledge valorisation represents a more comprehensive approach than traditional knowledge transfer, encompassing the creation of social and economic value by connecting different sectors and transforming research results into products, services, solutions, and knowledge-based policies.

Letta's report (2024) frames this need in terms of a “fifth freedom” for the Single Market—encompassing “research, innovation, data, competences, knowledge and education.” This fifth freedom would create “an ecosystem where knowledge diffusion propels both economic vitality, societal advancement and cultural enlightenment,” complementing the traditional four freedoms of goods, services, capital, and people.

2.1.2 Need to strengthen the regions

Innovation capacity varies dramatically across the European landscape, with some regions possessing advanced innovation ecosystems while others struggle with fragmented, disconnected structures. The

Letta report (2024) quantifies this challenge starkly: “Collectively, about 135 million people, nearly one third of the EU population, live in places which, in the last two decades, have slowly fallen behind.”

The Draghi report (2024) warns that future growth patterns may intensify these disparities: “Much of the future growth in intra-EU trade will be in services, which tend to cluster in large and rich cities. Innovation and its benefits also tend to agglomerate in a few metropolitan areas.” Without intervention, Europe risks following the American pattern where “a small set of superstar cities has been thriving in recent years and pulling away from the rest of the country.”

To counter this trend, Draghi emphasises that “the EU must ensure that more cities and regions can participate in the sectors that will drive future growth.” Similarly, Letta argues for balancing the “freedom to move” with a “freedom to stay,” ensuring the Single Market empowers citizens rather than compelling relocation for economic opportunity.

2.1.3 Need to strengthen universities in their role of contributing with knowledge to solve societal and business needs

Universities contribute to this ecosystem approach as centres of knowledge production, collaboration, and coordination. Initially working within triple-helix relationships involving academia, industry, and government, universities now often include civil society in these networks, using a Quadruple Helix model to connect innovation with societal needs (Klofsten et al., 2019; Cobben et al., 2022).

This approach relates to emerging innovation models in higher education, such as the “fourth-generation university,” where universities function as regional innovation hubs connected with industry, government, and communities (Bogers & Steinbuch, 2023). ERA Hubs apply this concept at a policy level, with universities and knowledge institutes serving as bases for regional R&I ecosystems and connecting those regional R&I ecosystems across Europe.

Despite progress, understanding of how regional R&I ecosystems manage knowledge flows remains incomplete, contributing to varied outcomes from regional innovation policies (Klein Woolthuis et al., 2005; Stam, 2015). Addressing this issue involves supporting universities as coordinators that can connect fragmented networks, improving collaboration within and between regions. By recognising that universities' roles change over time—from knowledge producers toward innovation coordinators—Europe may better use regional differences to support inclusive innovation-driven growth (Guerrero et al., 2024; Belitski & Sikorski, 2024).

2.1.4 Need to incorporate an ecosystem approach

Traditional vertical interventions targeting specific entities have proven insufficient to address the complex challenges of modern innovation systems. The Final Report of the Mutual Learning Exercise on Knowledge Valorisation (European Commission, 2022) explicitly identified a “shift from stand-alone valorisation activities to multi-stakeholder co-creation processes and ecosystems” and a “shift from vertical thematic interventions to systemic changes.”

This ecosystem approach recognises that innovation emerges from complex interactions between diverse actors rather than from isolated organisations. The Draghi report notes that researchers in Europe are “less well integrated into innovation 'clusters'—networks of universities, start-ups, large companies and venture capitalists (VCs)—which account for a large share of successful commercialisations in high-tech sectors.”

Letta's report emphasises that supporting regional development requires not just financial investments but also “substantial technical assistance” that fosters “local capacities and leveraging the unique assets of each region.” This echoes the ERA Policy Agenda's focus on connected ecosystems and knowledge valorisation.

2.2 Value Proposition of ERA Hubs

ERA Hubs offer an integrated approach to strengthening Europe's innovation capacity through regionally anchored but pan-European connected ecosystems.

2.2.1 Connecting Knowledge Creators with Users

The European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda has identified persistent barriers in knowledge transfer between academia and industry/society. The 2020 ERA Communication highlighted “fragmented national innovation ecosystems” as a key challenge for European competitiveness. Bogers et al. (2017) identified significant “valley of death” issues in Europe where academic knowledge fails to reach practical application. The 2023 European Innovation Scoreboard reports that despite high research output, Europe lags global competitors in translating knowledge into marketable innovations.

2.2.2 Legitimising Valorisation Role

The European Commission's “Renewed ERA for Research and Innovation” acknowledges insufficient recognition and career incentives for researchers engaged in knowledge transfer activities compared to traditional academic metrics. Perkmann et al. (2021) found that academic engagement with industry remains undervalued in promotion criteria across European universities. Etzkowitz's (2019) research on the “entrepreneurial university” shows European institutions lag behind their US counterparts in embedding valorisation into academic identity.

2.2.3 Cross-Domain Learning

Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3) evaluations have revealed limited cross-sectoral fertilisation, with the 2022 S3 review noting “siloes innovation approaches” as a persistent weakness. Cooke's (2020) work on regional innovation systems shows that cross-domain pollination significantly increases innovation potential but remains underdeveloped in European regions. Foray (2021) found that knowledge spillovers between sectors remain below optimal levels in most European innovation ecosystems.

2.2.4 Paradigm Shift Facilitation

The European Commission's "Open Innovation, Open Science, Open to the World" initiative identified the need to shift from linear innovation models to co-creation ecosystems, but implementation has been uneven across regions. Carayannis and Campbell's (2021) research on quadruple helix models demonstrates that multistakeholder approaches yield substantially better innovation outcomes. Mazzucato's (2018) work on mission-oriented innovation highlights the gap between Europe's potential and actual implementation of collaborative innovation models.

2.2.5 Pan-European Networking

The "Widening Participation" agenda recognises significant disparities in innovation capacity between EU regions, with fragmentation limiting knowledge circulation. Veugelers' (2022) analysis shows European innovation suffers from "subscale" challenges compared to US and Asian counterparts due to fragmented regional approaches. The 2023 Joint Research Centre report notes that duplication of efforts across regions costs Europe an estimated €10 billion annually in innovation investment inefficiencies. ERA Hubs thus represent a structured response to these well-documented gaps, offering an integrated approach to strengthening Europe's innovation capacity through regionally anchored but pan-European connected ecosystems.

3 Methodology

3.1 Overview

The current ERA Hub Framework Model prototype evolved through a rigorous, iterative process combining theoretical foundations with practical testing and stakeholder co-creation. This methodology ensured the framework would be both evidence-based and applicable across diverse European regions.

From D1.1 to D1.4, the framework transformed from a broad conceptual model to a fully structured prototype. An important change was redefining ERA Hubs as regional R&I ecosystems of quadruple helix actors, led by universities, aimed at improving knowledge valorisation within their regions. This highlighted universities as orchestrators of regional R&I ecosystems due to their neutrality, long-term presence, and ability to connect diverse stakeholders.

Another significant shift was the enhanced focus on knowledge valorisation. While initial concepts (D1.1) emphasised inter-regional collaboration, the final framework (D1.4) prioritises transforming research outputs into concrete societal and challenge-based benefits. The framework now includes structured mechanisms for knowledge transfer, stakeholder engagement, and innovation-driven collaboration, recognising that effective regional R&I ecosystems require both connectivity and active facilitation. The implementation tools were further developed by connecting them to ecosystem maturity levels. The final version includes a PLAYBOOK, SELF-ASSESSMENT, TOOLBOX, and PLATFORM, providing a comprehensive approach to supporting knowledge valorisation across European regions.

3.2 Co-Design Process

The Co-Design process with the CDTF (detailed in “D1.3 – Report on Co-creation with the Extended CDTF”) played a key role in refining the mission and scope of ERA Hubs, their value proposition and positioning, as well as their operational aspects, governance, and seven lines of action. Their feedback was catalytical in evolving the definition of ERA Hubs from a “strategic platform” to a “central access point”, now to a “university-led” quadruple helix ecosystem of actors for knowledge valorisation.

Key co-creation sessions included early hands-on arenas, such as the EuroTech event in Lyngby and the WOIC conference in Bilbao in 2023. Additional testing workshops were conducted online with an extended group in March 2024, followed by validation sessions in June (online) and at the WOIC conference in Berkely in September 2024. These revealed critical insights, such as the importance of governance structures, trust-building among quadruple helix actors, and tailored KPIs to measure ecosystem maturity. Sessions at international conferences like the World Open Innovation further refined the ERA Hub’s seven lines of action, with knowledge valorisation emerging as a core pillar—shifting from broad “innovation” to targeted support for knowledge transfer and commercialisation. The workshops also highlighted challenges, such as avoiding potential overlaps with other EU initiatives and the need for clear communication with stakeholders. In this line, the iterative feedback process ensured the ERA Hub model balanced flexibility for regional adaptation with a unified European framework, as demonstrated in pilot cases across the Czech Republic, Denmark, and the Netherlands.

3.3 Pilot Implementation

The ERA Hub Framework Model was tested through three regional pilots at different ecosystem maturity levels, each offering unique insights. In Prague's emerging AI ecosystem, challenges like fragmented collaboration and limited commercialisation informed targeted tools for governance centralisation and startup funding. The Danish pilot, focused on life sciences and sustainable tech, highlighted coordination gaps and scaling difficulties, leading to governance and networking enhancements inspired by Medicon Valley Alliance. Brainport Eindhoven's semiconductor and health tech pilot reinforced the value of university-industry-government partnerships while addressing knowledge retention and civil society engagement.

Together, these pilots validated the framework's adaptability. Prague's case shaped tools for emerging regional R&I ecosystems, while the Danish and Dutch pilots refined strategies for mature ones. This iterative testing ensured a balance between standardised methodologies and flexibility, addressing diverse regional R&I needs—from foundational collaboration to optimising knowledge flows.

3.4 Integration into an ERA Hub Framework Model

Based on all the above methodological steps, the ERA Hub Framework Model integrates pilot implementation insights and co-design process inputs into a structured model, including:

- A clear **definition** of ERA Hubs.
- An ERA Hub Framework governance model as part of the current prototype model.
- A **SELF-ASSESSMENT** where ecosystems can assess their level of maturity along seven lines of actions that are key for regional R&I ecosystems: talent, research, collaboration, governance, funding, innovation, and knowledge transfer.
- A **PLATFORM**, including the compliance criteria to develop the ERA Hubs network to foster interregional collaboration.
- A **PLAYBOOK** and a **TOOLBOX** with concrete and hands-on guidance to foster the maturity of ecosystems across various lines of action. According to the results of the self-assessment tool, specific tools from the Toolbox and guidance from the Playbook are suggested to each ecosystem, facilitating the implementation of changes and the readability of the tools.

This methodology has ensured a balanced integration of top-down policy direction with bottom-up stakeholder engagement, providing structured guidance while maintaining adaptability to diverse regional contexts. The framework has already demonstrated its effectiveness through pilot implementations, validating its robustness and practicality in supporting Europe's regional R&I ecosystems.

4 ERA Hub Framework Model: Current Prototype

4.1 Overview

The current prototype of the ERA Hub Framework Model prototype seeks to strengthen university-led regional R&I ecosystems across Europe. By positioning universities as orchestrators of quadruple helix collaboration, the framework creates a structured mechanism for knowledge valorisation, defined as “the process of creating social and economic value from knowledge by linking different areas and sectors, and transforming data, know-how, and research results into sustainable products, services, solutions, and knowledge-based policies that benefit society” (Council of the EU, 2022).

4.2 Definition of ERA Hubs

An ERA Hub is now defined in the ERA Hub Framework Model as:

“An ecosystem of quadruple helix actors, led by universities, aiming at improving knowledge valorisation within their region. The ERA Hubs operate within their broader R&I regional ecosystems, which constitute the background conditions for knowledge valorisation.”

This definition captures the essence of what ERA Hubs represent: collaborative regional R&I ecosystems rather than physical centres or one-directional flows.

4.3 ERA Hub Framework Model: Governance Model

The ERA Hub Framework governance model establishes a structured collaboration mechanism among quadruple helix actors, as illustrated in Figure 1. At its core is a team of professionals from different organisations who hold regular meetings focused on knowledge valorisation priorities. The governance structure operates at three levels:

1. **Strategic Level:** A steering committee with representatives from all quadruple helix actors sets priorities, approves action plans, and monitors progress. This ensures balanced representation and legitimacy.
2. **Operational Level:** A core team, typically hosted by the university orchestrator, manages day-to-day coordination, communication, and implementation of agreed actions.
3. **Project Level:** Working groups or task forces focused on specific initiatives bring together relevant stakeholders based on expertise and interest.

This multi-level governance structure facilitates structured collaboration through:

- Regular meetings with clear agendas and decision processes.
- Needs assessment and prioritisation mechanisms.
- Coordinated action planning with defined responsibilities.
- Feedback loops to evaluate and adjust activities.

The resulting collaboration produces tangible knowledge valorisation outcomes, including industry-academia partnerships, research-driven startups, intellectual asset management, standardisation, policy uptake, and both social and technological innovation.

Figure 1 ERA Hubs in practice - Structured Collaboration Mechanism and Knowledge Valorisation Outcomes

4.4 Key Characteristics of ERA Hubs

The ERA Hubs are defined by six key characteristics (as can be found in Table 1) that distinguish their approach to regional innovation:

Characteristic	Description
Regions at the Centre	Place-based innovation strategies tailored to local contexts where actors are established, produce value, and retain talent
Multistakeholder Engagement	Connect knowledge valorisation needs across all quadruple helix actors and develop multistakeholder co-creation processes
University Leadership	Universities as independent, central actors in the ERA context, well-rooted locally and essential in creating knowledge, competences, and talent
Non-domain-specific & Bottom-up Focus	Cross-domain and cross-sector learning focusing on systemic changes rather than vertical interventions
Flexible and Light Organisation	Not necessarily creating new organisations, but focusing on core tasks and connecting to existing structures
Cross-regional Knowledge Exchange	Connecting in a pan-European network to inspire and learn from other regions, accelerating change based on existing know-how

Table 1 Six key characteristics of regional R&I ecosystems

4.5 Developing regional R&I ecosystems through seven lines of action

To translate these characteristics into practice, the ERA Hub Framework Model delineates seven interrelated **lines of action** – strategic domains in which an ERA Hub must excel to strengthen its regional R&I ecosystem:

1. **Research:** Promoting excellence in knowledge creation and alignment of research efforts with regional needs
2. **Talent:** Developing, attracting, retaining and skilled individuals
3. **Knowledge Transfer:** Effectively exchanging knowledge among ecosystem actors
4. **Funding:** Mobilising and aligning sufficient financial resources for R&I
5. **Collaboration:** Building partnerships and developing a collaborative culture
6. **Governance:** Deploying an effective strategic management and coordination of ecosystem activities and responsibilities
7. **Innovation:** Enhancing the development and uptake of new solutions and services and developing the right conditions for it.

Each line of action reinforces the others, creating a holistic framework that universities and regional stakeholders can use to methodically build all facets of a thriving innovation ecosystem.

4.6 Supporting the emergence and development of ecosystems – a maturity journey

The ERA Hub Framework Model recognises that ecosystems evolve through distinct maturity phases, each characterised by increasing levels of integration and collaborative intensity. Four maturity levels have been identified, each with a corresponding Ecosystem Readiness Level (ERL) score:

- **Emerging:** Initial development stages (ERL 1-2)
- **Developing:** Growing coordination capacity (ERL 2-3)
- **Mature:** Advanced coordination capabilities (ERL 3-4)
- **Advanced:** Highly integrated ecosystem functioning (ERL 5)

As illustrated in Figure 2, this maturity progression follows a path from simple communication and information exchange (Emergence) through coordinated networking (Development) and loose coordination for compatible goals (Diffusion) to joint activities based on a common strategy (Collaboration). This evolution represents a journey from lower to higher levels of both integration and intensity of activities.

Figure 2 Levels of interaction and activity patterns (Russel & Smorodinskaya 2018)

The maturity assessment directly connects to ERA Policy Agenda Action 7 on knowledge valorisation by evaluating how well an ecosystem supports collaboration, knowledge exchange, and the transformation of research into societal and economic impact. A mature ecosystem exhibits well-established frameworks, policies, and funding mechanisms that enable efficient knowledge valorisation—the core function of ERA Hubs.

4.7 Maturity assessment across the seven lines of action

The ERA Hub Framework Model integrates the seven lines of action with the four maturity levels through a comprehensive assessment system visualised in radar charts (Figure 3). These charts illustrate the development pattern of regional R&I ecosystems at each maturity stage, with scores measured on a scale of 1-5 for each line of action, yielding a maximum total score of 35 for the entire ecosystem.

The radar charts in Figure 3 represent theoretical examples that demonstrate typical patterns of ecosystem development:

1. **Emerging (11/35):** Early-stage ecosystem with uneven development. Some areas like Talent and Funding may progress first, but overall scores remain low (1-2). Basic information sharing and initial connections exist, with minimal collaboration.
2. **Developing (18/35):** More balanced growth across dimensions, though variations persist. Coordinated networking emerges, with stakeholders engaging in joint planning and resource sharing. Scores typically range from 2-3.
3. **Mature (25/35):** Strong development in most areas, with scores of 3-4. Active collaboration on projects is common, and stakeholders work toward shared goals. Some domains approach excellence.
4. **Advanced (34/35):** Near-complete integration across all dimensions (scores ~5). Deep collaboration, joint decision-making, and strong partnerships drive significant value.

By regularly assessing their ecosystem using this framework, regional stakeholders can develop targeted strategies to systematically strengthen their ecosystem along each line of action and advance toward higher levels of maturity.

The maturity assessment is directly implemented through the SELF-ASSESSMENT described in section 5.3, which operationalises these theoretical concepts into a practical digital tool that regional R&I ecosystems can use to evaluate their current state and identify pathways for development.

Figure 3 Maturity levels through a radar chart visualisation system – Theoretical models

5 ERA Hub Framework Model: Implementation Tools

5.1 Overview

The ERA Hub Framework Model is operationalised through four complementary implementation tools that function as an integrated system to support regional R&I ecosystems at every stage of development.

Based on feedback from stakeholders, pilot implementations, and co-creation sessions with the Co-Design Task Force (CDTF), these tools have been iteratively refined to create a coherent ecosystem for knowledge valorisation support. The SELF-ASSESSMENT has evolved from being primarily linked to the TOOLBOX to incorporating hallmarks from the PLAYBOOK, integrating feedback from use cases, and insights from piloting activities.

A key enhancement in the implementation tools is the emphasis on co-creative processes. The SELF-ASSESSMENT now encourages interactive discussions among key stakeholders within the R&I ecosystem to reach consensual answers that provide well-rounded responses about the ecosystem's current state while fostering shared understanding of strengths and weaknesses.

The four implementation tools work together in a logical sequence:

1. The PLAYBOOK serves as the strategic foundation, describing hallmarks of excellence along the seven lines of action and providing a roadmap for ecosystem development.
2. The SELF-ASSESSMENT enables regional ecosystems to diagnose their current maturity levels across the seven lines of action through co-creative stakeholder dialogue.
3. The TOOLBOX offers 33 concrete, actionable tools that ecosystems can implement to elevate their maturity, tailored to their assessment results.
4. The PLATFORM connects regional R&I ecosystems into a pan-European network while providing access to all implementation resources.

Together, these tools create a comprehensive framework that supports the journey of regional ecosystems toward becoming advanced ERA Hubs, regardless of their starting point.

5.2 The Four Implementation Tools: Current vs. Future State

<i>Tool</i>	<i>Purpose</i>	<i>Current Prototype</i>	<i>Future Development</i>
PLAYBOOK	Strategic guidance and roadmap to improve ERA Hub maturity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hallmarks of excellence for each line of action - High-level roadmap to assemble stakeholders and start the process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More governance instructions for diverse regional contexts - Potentially expand with additional case studies
SELF-ASSESSMENT	Maturity evaluation across seven lines of action using KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Qualitative questionnaire scoring from 1–5 - Radar chart output 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate quantitative data from EHESO, RIS - Provide more tailored

TOOLBOX	Action-oriented interventions ecosystem improvement	for	- Basic logic for linking to TOOLBOX - 33 tools addressing multiple lines of action - Implementation steps and case examples	recommendations based on “if” conditions per score - Add more tools based on further pilot experiences - Refine tool categorisation and cross-linking with SELF-ASSESSMENT outcomes
PLATFORM	Central repository and European networking function	digital pan-European networking	- Prototype with limited participant ecosystem profiles - Access to PLAYBOOK, SELF-ASSESSMENT, and TOOLBOX	- Scale up usage across Europe - Advanced matchmaking features - Aggregated data analytics for policy intelligence

Table 2 ERA Hub Framework Model: Four Implementation Tools

5.3 PLAYBOOK: Hallmarks of excellence and a Roadmap to increasing maturity

The PLAYBOOK is the foundational component of the ERA Hub Framework Model intended to guide regional R&I ecosystems to advance their maturity across the seven lines of action. It serves as a practical guide describing what successful regional R&I ecosystems look like through the hallmarks of excellence and provides a roadmap for enhancing knowledge valorisation.

A. Key Features:

1. Hallmarks of Excellence: Observable characteristics that describe successful regional R&I ecosystems at an ideal, advanced level of maturity with links to concrete tools from the TOOLBOX that support development in each line of action.

Examples by line of action:

- **Research:** Presence of large research and technology institutions à *Supporting tools:* Centres of excellence, Industry sponsorships
- **Talent:** Ability to attract talent from outside the ecosystem à *Supporting tools:* Attractive living conditions, Exchange programmes
- **Knowledge transfer:** Well-established relationships between ecosystem players à *Supporting tools:* Central interest organisation, Stakeholder engagement forum, Stakeholder engagement platform
- **Funding:** Availability of funding for research à *Supporting tools:* Grant and soft funding
- **Collaboration:** High level of trust and openness between quadruple helix players à *Supporting tools:* Trust-building activities, Stakeholder engagement forum, Stakeholder engagement platform
- **Governance:** Long-term joint objectives à *Supporting tools:* Central interest organisation, Stakeholder engagement forum
- **Innovation:** Dynamic patent landscape à *Supporting tools:* Innovation hub, Tech transfer office

- 2. Roadmap:** Step-by-step guidance from initial stakeholder engagement to developing a joint strategy, including practical guidelines on convening stakeholders, setting a vision and focus, establishing governance, and applying the SELF-ASSESSMENT, TOOLBOX and PLATFORM.

Steps in the Roadmap:

- Gather stakeholders from academia, industry, and government
- Determine focus area and establish steering group
- Use the SELF-ASSESSMENT to assess current maturity level
- Select and implement specific tools from the TOOLBOX
- Connect and collaborate with other regional R&I ecosystems

B. Implementation

- Ecosystem stakeholders access the PLAYBOOK through the PLATFORM
- For each line of action, they find hallmarks of excellence, describing an ideal to aspire to.
- They follow the steps in the roadmap to advance their ecosystem's maturity, as part of the ERA Hub's developmental pathway.

5.4 SELF-ASSESSMENT: Assessing Maturity Level of Broader R&I Ecosystem

The SELF-ASSESSMENT aims to support and accelerate the progress of R&I ecosystems in becoming more mature by enabling them to evaluate their current maturity level against defined KPIs. The tool is structured as a questionnaire that forms the foundation for implementing the ERA Hub Framework Model.

A. Key Features

- **Structured Assessment:** Maturity evaluation across the seven lines of action, using qualitative questions on a 1-5 Likert scale.
- **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):** Serve as the basis for the scoring mechanism by measuring maturity along the seven lines of action.
- **Co-creative Process:** The assessment encourages interactive discussions among ecosystem stakeholders to reach consensual answers, fostering shared understanding of strengths and weaknesses

B. Implementation

- The university contact person, in consultation with the key stakeholders, registers for the online questionnaire that is hosted in the PLATFORM.
- The group discusses in a co-creative approach and reaches a consensual answer for all questions
- Results visualised through radar charts showing maturity across the seven lines of action
- The findings help identify key strengths and weaknesses, thereby directing future ecosystem development efforts

5.5 TOOLBOX: Actionable Tools for ecosystem development

The TOOLBOX is a set of 33 concrete tools that an R&I ecosystem can employ to elevate their maturity along the seven lines of action. It serves as a companion to the PLAYBOOK, bridging the gap between assessment and implementation.

A. Key Features

- **Diverse Tools:** Offers 33 concrete and diverse tools such as Centres of Excellence, Industrial PhD programmes, and Innovation Hubs, covering all seven lines of action with practical, proven interventions matching different maturity levels.
- **Comprehensive Documentation:** Presents each tool with detailed information including value proposition and real-world case studies.
- **Cross-Cutting Application:** Many tools address multiple lines of action simultaneously, allowing synergies between different areas (e.g., “Industrial PhD” programmes enhance both Research and Talent development).

B. Implementation

- Based on the SELF-ASSESSMENT results, the University applicant along with the key stakeholders consult the TOOLBOX to find tools that:
 - Address the lines of action on which they want to make progress
 - Are appropriate to their current maturity level
- Each tool description provides practical implementation guidance with concrete steps
- Real-world examples demonstrate how each tool has been successfully implemented elsewhere

5.6 PLATFORM: Digital Infrastructure with Dual Function

The PLATFORM serves as the operational backbone of the ERA Hubs network, functioning with a dual purpose: hosting all implementation tools and linking regional R&I ecosystems into an interactive pan-European network for knowledge exchange and collaboration.

A. Key Features

- **Resource Repository:** Provides centralised access to the PLAYBOOK, SELF-ASSESSMENT, and TOOLBOX, guiding users to appropriate tools based on their ecosystem's specific needs and maturity levels
- **Digital Connection Infrastructure:** Creates a pan-European network of regional R&I ecosystems focused on knowledge valorisation, displaying comprehensive profiles of each Hub, including geographic information, contact details, and maturity levels and interactive radar graphs showing strengths across seven lines of action.
- **Policy Intelligence:** If the PLATFORM is fully developed and populated in the future, aggregated data from it can provide valuable insights to policymakers on ecosystem development trends, and support evidence-based decision-making for future regional R&I investments.

B. Implementation

- Universities, along with key stakeholders consult the PLAYBOOK and apply to join the ERA Hub network through the PLATFORM
- They complete the SELF-ASSESSMENT, which becomes part of their ecosystem profile on the PLATFORM, listing focus areas, maturity levels, and contact information
- Based on profile information, the PLATFORM suggests connections with other regional R&I ecosystems that have complementary strengths or similar challenges
- Regional R&I ecosystems access all implementation resources and connect with peers for knowledge exchange
- The PLATFORM facilitates ongoing collaboration through conferences, events, forums, webinars, and case studies, accelerating the adoption of successful practices across Europe

The PLATFORM functions as both the digital infrastructure for individual Hub development and the connective tissue that weaves regional R&I ecosystems into a coherent European Research Area network, scaling individual regional efforts into a continental movement with far greater collective impact.

6 Towards a fully developed ERA Hub Framework Model

A fully operational ERA Hub Framework Model envisions an ecosystem of a pan-European network of regional R&I ecosystems fostering knowledge valorisation processed led by universities. At its core is the ERA Hub, an ecosystem of quadruple helix actors led by universities to improve knowledge valorisation within their region. The ERA Hubs operate within their broader R&I regional ecosystems, which constitute the background conditions for knowledge valorisation. The fully developed model enables a network of interconnected regional R&I ecosystems that collaborate across key lines of action: Research, Talent, Innovation, and Funding. Each ERA hub can exist at different maturity levels (Emerging, Developing, or Advanced), with the model providing pathways for progression.

Underpinning this network is the PLATFORM, which functions as the operational backbone of the ERA Hubs network with a dual purpose: hosting all implementation tools and linking regional R&I ecosystems into an interactive pan-European network for knowledge exchange and collaboration. The PLATFORM offers three complementary components that work iteratively:

1. **PLAYBOOK** - Provides hallmarks of excellence describing successful regional R&I ecosystems at advanced maturity levels and a step-by-step roadmap for development. The fully operational version will include more detailed governance instructions to ensure applicability across diverse regional contexts.
2. **SELF-ASSESSMENT** - Enables regions to evaluate their R&I ecosystem maturity across seven lines of action through a structured questionnaire with KPIs and a 1-5 scoring system. The fully operational version will incorporate quantitative data from sources like EHESO and RIS and provide tailored tool recommendations based on specific maturity scores.
3. **TOOLBOX** - Offers 33 actionable tools with detailed implementation guides, value propositions, and real-world case studies. These cross-cutting tools simultaneously address multiple lines of action, with the fully operational version continually expanding based on implementation experiences.

Beyond hosting these tools, the PLATFORM serves as a digital connection infrastructure that creates a pan-European network of regional R&I ecosystems, facilitating knowledge sharing through conferences, events, and exchanges while providing policy intelligence for evidence-based decision-making.

6.1 How to advance the ERA Hub Framework Model toward full implementation

Full implementation of the ERA Hub Model envisions a cohesive, interconnected network of regional R&I ecosystems across Europe, operating through established governance frameworks and operational tools. Achieving this requires transitioning from pilot initiatives to institutionalised structures with formal recognition in the ERA policy, supported by aligned stakeholder incentives and robust digital infrastructure. A fully operational ERA Hub Model would feature quadruple-helix collaboration mechanisms, active cross-regional knowledge exchange between advanced and emerging regions, and

seamless integration with complementary EU innovation initiatives (for more detailed information, refer to “D4.4 - COOPERATE White Book”).

6.1.1 Further development of methodology

A key priority is refining governance structures at both hub and network levels. ERA Hubs are designed as “lightweight coordination mechanisms” rather than new institutions, necessitating agile, inclusive governance anchored in the quadruple helix—universities, industry, government, and society. Establishing flexible yet transparent decision-making bodies, such as multi-stakeholder steering committees, will help maintain strategic direction and legitimacy. Concurrently, internal incentives must encourage active engagement from all partners; aligning academic career and funding incentives with knowledge transfer and multi-actor collaboration can significantly enhance commitment.

Ensuring universities and research institutions are incentivised through performance agreements or funding formulas supporting their “third mission” – economic valorisation alongside education and research - will bolster their leadership in ERA Hubs. Similarly, motivation mechanisms for companies, public agencies, and civil society, such as recognition, co-funding, or awards, will sustain broad stakeholder participation. Collectively, these governance and incentive refinements will solidify the methodology by which regions adopt and manage ERA Hubs.

A clear roadmap for scaling up and interlinking ERA Hubs across Europe is essential. Transitioning from pilot projects to a structured rollout involves identifying candidate regions, providing them with the refined framework, and supporting activities such as seed funding, coaching, and peer-learning. A “Call for Champions” approach, potentially through an EU-level call, can initiate the first wave of hubs. Embedding the ERA Hub model into European Research Area governance structures, such as formally recognising ERA Hubs within ERA policy or creating an official ERA Hub label, would further institutionalise the model and enhance its longevity.

An interim coordination body, possibly led by the COOPERATE consortium in collaboration with the European Commission, could oversee network expansion and foster connections among hubs. Initiatives such as twinning programs and the use of Widening instruments can ensure weaker regional R&I ecosystems benefit from mentoring and capacity building.

6.1.2 Further finetuning and enriching of the tools

Testing the KPIs in a wider set of regions & evolution over time

Continuous testing and evolution of KPIs and the SELF-ASSESSMENT are critical, expanding the pilot tests to more diverse regional contexts to identify gaps or biases and improve robustness. For example, pilot feedback from Czech Republic has already informed refinements, with further piloting essential for broader validation.

Enriching the four implementation tools: more tools and more tailored recommendations

The PLAYBOOK and TOOLBOX, key deliverables of COOPERATE, should remain dynamic resources regularly updated based on new insights and user needs. Tailored instruments addressing specific regional challenges, additional case studies, and refined recommendations can continuously enrich these resources. Establishing mechanisms such as editorial boards or community feedback loops will ensure the PLAYBOOK and TOOLBOX align with best practices.

Expanding the piloting activities to other regions

Building on the first pilot phase, the model needs further testing in additional regions (currently ongoing second piloting phase in Lodz, Poland and Orléans, France) to validate its flexibility and applicability across different contexts and maturity levels.

Populating the platform with regional hubs and supporting the use of the tools

The PLATFORM must achieve critical mass by onboarding numerous regional R&I ecosystems, enabling benchmarking and collaboration. Encouraging user engagement through outreach and training, alongside technical enhancements such as advanced matchmaking tools, will transition the PLATFORM from prototype to a fully interactive digital community hub.

Fostering the inter-hub connection

Physical inter-hub connections complement digital efforts, with regular opportunities for interaction such as annual conferences, policy labs, and EU-facilitated workshops enhancing network cohesion. Smaller-scale exchanges, including twinning arrangements, staff exchanges, and study visits, further accelerate knowledge-sharing and capacity-building.

Exploring further complementarity with other EU-level initiatives

Integrating the ERA Hub Framework Model with broader European R&I initiatives, including European Innovation Ecosystems and Regional Innovation Valleys, is crucial for maximising synergies and avoiding duplication. Connections with thematic innovation clusters and mission-oriented networks (e.g., Hydrogen Valleys) and talent mobility programs (e.g., ERA Talent Platform, MSCA programs) will further enrich the ERA Hub initiative, contributing to a cohesive European innovation landscape.

6.2 Looking forward: Long-term impact of a fully developed ERA Hub Framework Model

If fully implemented, the ERA Hubs model promises important long-term impacts.

6.2.1 Enhanced knowledge valorisation at regional level & establishment of a long-term vision

As highlighted in the Draghi report, “Europe must ensure that more cities and regions can participate in the sectors that will drive future growth.” By facilitating structured connections among universities, industry, government, and civil society, the ERA Hubs Model directly addresses fragmented knowledge flows and institutional silos. This contributes to EU's growth and reduces inequalities across EU regions.

6.2.2 Reinforcement of universities as orchestrators of knowledge valorisation

A fully implemented ERA Hub Model strengthens universities' legitimacy as orchestrators of regional innovation ecosystems, transforming them from traditional technology transfer entities into key multi-stakeholder conveners and innovation catalysts. This enhanced role aligns with what Letta describes as the “fifth freedom” of the Single Market, encompassing “research, innovation, data, competences, knowledge and education” and creating an ecosystem “where knowledge diffusion propels both economic vitality, societal advancement and cultural enlightenment.”

6.2.3 Complement to Cohesion Policy through technical assistance

The ERA Hub model complements Europe's Cohesion Policy, providing what Letta describes as not just “financial investments but also substantial technical assistance” to revitalise struggling regions. By institutionalising ERA Hubs alongside Cohesion instruments, regions gain structured support for aligning R&I investments with place-based strategic priorities to enhance overall effectiveness and address the fact that “collectively, about 135 million people, nearly one third of the EU population, live in places which, in the last two decades, have slowly fallen behind.”

The ERA Hub Framework Model represents an important step toward a balanced, resilient European Research Area. It embodies the principles of “embedding research and innovation drivers at the core of the Single Market” while ensuring that innovation doesn't simply cluster in already-advantaged regions but spreads opportunities broadly, supporting both the “freedom to move and freedom to stay” across the European Union.

7 Conclusion

The ERA Hub Framework Model represents a transformative approach to strengthening regional R&I ecosystems across Europe. By positioning universities as orchestrators of quadruple helix collaboration and focusing on knowledge valorisation, the framework addresses a critical gap in Europe's innovation landscape.

The model responds directly to the pressing challenges identified in recent high-level policy documents, including the Draghi and Letta reports, which highlight that “much of the knowledge generated by European researchers remains commercially unexploited.” It embodies the transition toward fourth-generation universities that serve as local ecosystem orchestrators, rooted in their territories while connecting knowledge actors to drive innovation.

The framework's seven interconnected lines of action—Research, Talent, Knowledge Transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance, and Innovation—provide a comprehensive blueprint for developing mature regional R&I ecosystems. Its maturity assessment system enables regions to chart clear developmental pathways from emerging to advanced stages, with each progression representing higher levels of integration and collaborative intensity.

Four complementary implementation tools operationalise this vision:

1. The PLAYBOOK providing strategic guidance through hallmarks of excellence
2. The SELF-ASSESSMENT enabling data-driven ecosystem analysis
3. The TOOLBOX offering tailored interventions for different maturity levels
4. The PLATFORM providing access to tools and connecting regional ecosystems into a pan-European network

In realising these objectives, Europe can take a decisive step toward a more inclusive, networked, and dynamic innovation landscape—one that fully capitalises on its rich research base and transforms knowledge into tangible benefits for citizens.

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